

Efficacy of Mirror Therapy In Improving Motor Recovery And Functional Ability of The Hemiparetic Lower Limb after Stroke

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Abstract

Lower extremity motor function after stroke is often impaired, causing restriction in functional mobility. This study investigated the efficacy of mirror therapy on lower extremity motor recovery and functional ability after stroke. In this pre-test/post-test randomized controlled trial, a total of twenty (22) hemiparetic stroke patients were recruited, however, 20 completed the program. Mini mental state examination (MMSE) and Brunstrom stage of motor recovery were used as screening tools. Fugl-Meyer Assessment scale (FMA), Brunnell balance assessment scale (BBA) and Functional Ambulation Category (FAC), were used as primary outcome measures. Wilcoxon signed rank test was used to compare the pre- and post-treatment outcomes within each group. Mannwhitney U test was used to compare treatment responses between control group and experimental group. The results showed that, for the FMA, there was no statistically significant difference at baseline between the experimental and control groups ($P>0.05$), after the intervention, there was statistically significant difference between the groups ($P<0.05$). For BBA, there was no statistically significant difference at baseline between the groups ($P>0.05$), for the post intervention, it was found that there was no statistically significant difference between the groups ($P>0.05$). For FAC, there was no statistically significant difference at baseline between the groups ($P>0.05$), for post-intervention, there was statistically significant difference between the groups ($P<0.05$). Administration of three(3) weeks of mirror therapy during the acute and sub-acute stages of stroke resulted in significant recovery in motor function. However, no difference on a BBA was recorded.

Keywords: stroke, hemiparesis, mirror therapy, shame therapy

Introduction

Stroke is the third leading cause of death and a major cause of long-term disability in the elderly [1]. It is responsible for 0.9 to 4% of total hospitals admissions and 0.5 to 45% of neurological admissions [2]. The prevalence of stroke in Nigeria is 1.14 per 1000 [3]. More than 60% of stroke survivors suffer from persistent neurologic deficit [4]. Lower extremity motor function after stroke is often impaired, causing restriction in functional mobility [5].

Traditionally, physical therapy for patients with hemiparesis in the weeks after their stroke consist of exercise therapy based on neurodevelopmental therapy (NDT) and proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation (PNF), as well as on the practice of pre walking functional task such as transfer activities, weight shifts in sitting or standing and the maintenance of unassisted stance [6]. Research study indicates that conventional rehabilitation is not accurately or efficiently targeting abnormal muscle activation and coordination [7].

Mirror therapy is new therapeutic intervention that focus on moving the unimpaired limb [8]. Sathian et al found that 2 weeks of intense mirror therapy in chronic

stroke patients resulted in significant recovery of grip strength & hand movement of paretic arm [9]. A research by [10] suggested that for the hemiparetic stroke survivor, the neural circuits in the brain that are responsible for mediating an action intention and an executed action that precisely reflects that intention are no longer intact. Traditional occupational therapy techniques address this incompatibility by using behavior repetition. However, through use of the mirror, the client views a more successful action than if he or she were looking at the impaired extremity attempting to complete the same or similar tasks [10]. It has also been suggested that visualizing and performing symmetrical bilateral movements post stroke enhance neuroplastic changes within the brain [11]. Research suggested that mirror therapy will improve motor activity, gait pattern and reduction in spasticity [6], however, there is need for more research on the efficacy of mirror therapy in management of lower limb of sub-acute stroke patients. This research is aimed at finding the effect of Mirror therapy on functional recovery of lower limb following stroke.

Materials and Methods

A total number of twenty two (22) acute/sub-cute hemiparetic stroke patients from Murtala Muhammad Specialist Hospital (MMSH) and Muhammad Abdullahi Wase Specialist Hospital (MAWSH) were recruited. These hospitals are located in Kano state. The selection was done using purposive sampling technique according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria such as ; patients with first episode of unilateral stroke, patients within the age range of 30-65years. However, two (2) participants were excluded for not meeting inclusion criteria. The participants involving both genders were randomly assigned to the two groups by a research assistant (i.e. control and experimental groups). Equal number of patients were distributed to the two groups (10 patients per group) in this study as shown below in the flowchart. The randomization was double-blinded to ensure unbiased. Mini mental

state examination (MMSE) and Brunstrom stage of motor recovery were used as screening tools for the participants.

Daily treatment session was 1 hour 30 min for both control and experimental group. Both Group received conventional therapy for 1 hour, immediately after the conventional therapy the control group received 30 min of sham therapy (patient is instructed to view the non reflecting surfaces of the mirror) while the experimental Group received mirror therapy for 30 minutes. Both groups performed only non-paretic lower limb movements during mirror therapy in the mirror group while sham therapy in case of control group e.g, Subjects did not move their paretic limb. For the control group, the non-reflecting surface of the mirror was kept facing the non-paretic limb. This prevented the control subjects from acquiring the visual feedback of the non-paretic lower extremity movements and performed the same exercises for the same duration. The experimental protocol was commenced as follows;

Figure No 1: study's flowchart

Group A(Control Group); this group received conventional therapy which includes stretching of Tendo chilies & hamstrings, bridging exercises(10X2 repetitions),ankle pump exercise using spring (10X2 repetition),sit to stand exercise(10x2 repetition), supported squatting (10x2 repetition) ,isometric exercise for hip extensors & quadriceps (10x2 repetitions),static bicycling (5minute), Resisted exercise for quadriceps with weight cuff, over ground gait training for a total of 1 hour. The above protocols were followed by sham therapy.

Group B (Experimental group) -this group received an additional 30 minutes of mirror therapy after receiving 1 hour of conventional therapy. The mirror therapy program consisting of performance of functional movement synergies using non-paretic hip, knee and ankle joints. These movements were performed in semi- reclined and sitting positions with the mirror placed in between the two lower limbs. The mirror was mounted on a stand with a tilt towards the paretic side to prevent the paretic limb from being viewed by the subject. For the mirror group, the reflective surface of the mirror was kept facing the non-paretic limb. The exercises performed in half-lying position were: hip-knee- ankle flexion, with the hip and knee placed in flexion, moving the knee inward and outward and hip abduction with external rotation followed by hip adduction with internal rotation. The exercises performed in sitting position were: Hip-knee-ankle flexion, knee extension with ankle dorsiflexion and knee flexion beyond 90°. Each of the above 6 exercises were performed in 2 sets of 10 repetitions. Fugl-Meyer Assessment scale, Brunnel balance assessment scale and Functional ambulation category scores were documented before starting of treatment & at the end of treatment protocol.

The data collected from this study was analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean, standard deviation and percentage to summarized the demographical characteristics of the participants, while inferential statistics(non parametric) was used to analyzed the primary outcomes measures, were by wilcoxon signed rank test was used to compared the pre- and post-treatment outcomes within each group. Mannwhitney U test was used to compare treatment responses between control group and experimental group. All statistical analysis were performed using statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) version 16 at a probability level of 0.05(95%)

Results

A total of 20 subjects 11 males (55%) and 9 females (45%) with either left or right sided hemiplegia participated in this study. All the participants were selected based on the stroke recovery stage of 2-3 and Mini mental state examination scale scores of >24. They were all < 4 months post stroke, with percentage durations as follows: 1 month 2(10%), 2 months 6(30%) 3 months 7(35%) 4 months 5(40%).

Table 1 presents the mean and standard deviation summary of the Age and onset groups of the subjects in both experimental and control group. The table showed that most of the participants were in the middle age category and also had mean stroke onsets of about 3 months.

Table 2; shows that, for the fugl Meyer assessment score (FMA), there was a statistically significant difference in lower limb motor improvement in the experimental group between baseline and post intervention (P<0.05). For the control group, there was a statistically significant difference in lower limb motor improvement between baseline and post intervention (P<0.05). For BBA, there is statistically significant difference in the experimental group between baseline and post intervention response (P<0.05), for the control group there was statistically significant difference between baseline and post intervention response (P<0.05). For FAC, there was statistically significant difference in the experimental group between baseline and post intervention response (P<0.05), for the control group, there was statistically significant difference between baseline and post intervention respons (P<0.05).

Table 3 shows that, for the FMA there was no statistically significant difference at baseline between experimental group and control group (P>0.05),for post intervention there was statistically significant difference between experimental group and control group (P<0.05). For Brunnel balance assessment scale (BBA), there was no statistically significant difference at baseline between experimental group and control group (P>0.05),for the post intervention, it reveals that there was no statistically significant difference between experimental group and control group (P<0.05). For Functional Ambulation Category (FAC), there was no statistically significant difference at baseline between experimental group and control group (P>0.05),for post-intervention, there was statistically significant difference between experimental group and control group (P<0.05).

Table No 1: Mean age and standard deviation summary of the participant ages and onset of the stroke.

Variables	experimental group	control group	combined group
	(N=10)	(N=10)	(N=20)
	Mean±SD	Mean±SD	Mean±SD
Age(years)	54.70±1.200	51.60±6.596	53.15±9.555
Onset (month)	3.20±1.392	3.30±0.949	3.25±1.1705

N=number of subjects, SD= standard deviation

Table No 2. Wilcoxon test summary of pre/post intervention comparison in experimental and control group.

Variables	pre-test	post-test	mean rank	Z	P
	(N=10) Mean±SD	(N=10) Mean±SD			
EG					
FMA	15.80±2.820	19.20±2.530	5.500	-2.816	0.005*
BBA	2.90±0.740	4.70±0.670	5.000	-2.842	0.004*
FAC	1.60±0.520	3.60±0.700	5.500	-2.873	0.004*
CG					
FMA	15.30±2.750	16.30±2.630	5.000	-2.887	0.004*
BBA	3.10±0.740	4.00±0.940	5.000	-3.000	0.003*
FAC	1.80±0.630	2.70±0.950	4.500	-2.714	0.007*

*significant, *p*= probability, *N*=number of subjects, *SD*= standard deviation, *EG*=experimental group, *CG*=control group

Table 3. Table below summarize the difference between the control and experimental groups.

Variables	Experimental	Control	median	Z	P
	(N=10) Mean±SD	(N=10) Mean±SD			
POST-INTERVENTION					
FMA	19.20±2.530	16.30±2.630	17.50	-2.433	0.015*
BBA	4.70±0.670	4.00±0.940	4.00	-1.684	0.092
FAC	1.60±0.520	3.60±0.700	3.00	-2.873	0.020*
BASELINE					
FMA	15.80±2.820	15.30±2.750	15.00	-0.495	0.621
BBA	2.90±0.740	3.10±0.740	3.00	-0.616	0.538
FAC	1.60±0.520	1.80±0.630	2.00	-0.702	0.483

*significant, *N*=number of subjects, *SD*= standard deviation

Discussion

The aim of this study was to assess the efficacy of mirror therapy using functional movement synergies on lower extremity motor recovery, balance, and mobility in acute/sub acute stroke patients. For the above protocol, the mirror and control group showed no significant difference in baseline scores for all the primary outcomes measures. At the end of 3 weeks of intervention there was significant improvement in the mirror group as well as control group in motor recovery, balance and mobility. The mirror group exhibited better performance in lower extremity motor recovery and ambulation categories than the control group; whereas, balance did not show significant difference when compared between the groups. Compared to the study by [8] that carry out his study on chronic stroke patients, both studies reported significant effect of mirror therapy on lower limb motor function, (interestingly, both studies used Fugl-meyer Motor Assessment as an outcome measure), which coincided with the results of this study

It is a general consensus that early implementation of intensive stroke rehabilitation is associated with enhanced and faster improvement in the performance of activities after stroke.[12]. Based on the evidence that maximum improvement in lower extremity motor recovery is achieved from first 3 month after stroke [13], we

decided to administer mirror therapy within the acute/sub acute phase of stroke. We sought to determine, if addition of mirror therapy program to conventional stroke rehabilitation within the acute/sub acute phase of stroke would produce additional benefits in term of lower extremity motor recovery and function, it was found from this study also there is significant improvement in the lower limb motor recovery.

As the recovery of motor function in stroke shows a gradual progression from synergistic movement patterns towards voluntary movements outside of stereotypical synergy [14], so the incorporation of functional movement synergies in the mirror therapy exercise protocol was considered for this study which yielded positive results. Furthermore, since most of the patients achieve independence in walking during the early phase of stroke [15], we included BBA and FAC to assess for the task specific and carry over effect on balance and gait. The mirror group and control group both showed improvement in FMA, BBA, and FAC after undergoing 3 weeks of intervention. Recent functional MRI study [16] have shown that mirror therapy increases the functional coupling between each pre motor region and the left supplementary motor area, which in turn showed an increased functional interaction with the ipsilesional sensorimotor cortex, which enhances neural plasticity and these chang-

es are specific to observation and imitation of tasks that are trained in the therapy.

Ramachandran conducted a study on use of mirror visual feedback in restoring brain function in 60 stroke patients and suggested that mirror therapy is more beneficial in patients with hemiparesis for improving motor recovery than a conventional treatment[17]. Dohle et al. conducted a study on Mirror therapy for improving motor function after stroke in two groups consisting of 15 patients in each group and concluded that mirror therapy improves sensory and attentional deficits which support motor recovery in a digital paretic limb, which all are in agreement with the findings of this study [8]. The mechanism by which simulation with the use of mirror therapy achieves this beneficial relationship has been postulated as follows: during mental rehearsal, the motor pathways needed for upcoming action are activated. During subsequent physical execution they would be recruited more quickly, which result in a better coordinated performances, indeed mental practice results in increased muscle strength, which ultimately enhances increased functional ability of the paretic lower limb [8].

At the end of intervention, there was significant difference observed between the groups in FMA. Because the mirror group achieved more mean change scores than the control group for this outcome measure. This could probably be due to the more duration of mirror therapy administration compared to the previous studies that shown no significant effect after 2 weeks of mirror therapy administration [17]. Other Previous studies on mirror therapy have shown significant improvement in motor function when administered for durations ranging from 3 weeks to 6 weeks [8-10], which is in consonance with the findings of the present study. Thus we can hypothesize that longer duration of intervention would probably result in a better and clinically significant motor recovery.

Change in BBA score did not show significant difference between the groups. The mirror group showed significant change in FAC at the end of intervention, despite absence of significant improvement in balance. As established in an earlier study, a positive correlation exists between the Fugl Meyer lower extremity assessment score and change in FAC [16]. Thus, achievement of substantial improvement in motor recovery could have led to enhanced ambulation skills in the mirror group subjects.

Nevertheless, this study has some limitations. The limitations of this study are few subjects were recruited and the fact that we did not use imaging techniques to detect cortical reorganization after therapy.

Conclusion

Administration of 3 weeks of mirror therapy with functional movement synergies in addition to conventional stroke rehabilitation during the acute and sub-acute stages of stroke may result in more significant recovery in motor function compared to conventional stroke rehabilitation alone. However, there is no difference between the experimental and control groups on a balance outcome (BBA).

Recommendations

Based on the outcomes of this study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Mirror therapy should be used as an adjunct to the conventional therapy in improving the motor functional ability specifically the motor recovery and functional mobility of the hemiparetic lower limb following stroke.
2. Further studies should attempt to answer on whether all categories of post stroke (acute, sub-acute and chronic) patients require the same intensity and duration of therapy.
3. Specificity regarding intensity and duration of therapy required to achieve optimum therapeutic effect should be evaluated in further studies.
4. Additional balance training should be also incorporated during management of stroke patients using mirror therapy.

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Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.